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Review Article

A Review on Neuralink – Achieve Ai Symbiosis with Medical Field.

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ABSTRACT

As days going we come across new and latest inventions which use Artificial Intelligence to ease our usage of the devices. But medical field has also excelled beyond its limits still we are unable to treat some diseases from root like Alzheimer, epilepsy, Parkinson's, etc. but brain machine interfaces (BMI) can be the technology which can improve or treat the sensory and motor function of the brain and can help to find solution of neurological disorders. The principle behind this brain implant system is with normal brain functions, brain signals are generated, but they can't be sent to arms, hands or legs, these signals are understood and translated to cursor movements, which helps the individual to regulate the computer by his or her thoughts. Special software carries all the signaling processes. Integrating AI approach with brain implementing BMI, Elon Musk's company Neuralink has successfully developed a chip which is called Neuralink. The link aims to implanting devices in paralyzed humans and neuronal diseases suffering patients, allowing them to treat or control phones or computers by brain signal. BMI has had a huge impact on mind-reading technology, controlling basic behaviors of the human brain and also detecting human emotions. This article discusses both advantages and disadvantages based on its applications. This paper investigates the innovative angles, applications, challenges, and moral contemplation related to Neuralink's cerebral chip innovation.

INTRODUCTION

Neuralink is a chip which is inserted into the motor cortex of the brain, which is specifically called as Brain Machine Interface (BMI). The chip contains long and thin wires called threads with electrodes and is also fitted correctly into the piece of skull. The threads will detect neural signals and ultimately

these transmitted by the link. It is used to communicate with machines and even control them. It helps to study and cure various medical problems [1]. Neuralink was invented and patented by Nedra Moheseni and Randolph Nudo in 2015. After one year in 2016, Elon Musk founded an American company and bought the patent by July

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2019 it had received 158 million Dollars. Neuralink brain chip is mixed of both bits of intelligence (Technology and Human) and achieves an interaction between human and artificial intelligence. It connects with BMI technology which is important in scientific and technology value. It is a revolutionary project that helps people suffering from diseases like paralysis, Parkinson's, disease, etc. [2] same as neuralink a company called synchron, backed by bill Gates and jeff Bezos, may become the first to commercialise a brain implant that lets people control touchscreen devices using brain signals. in addition, same as synchron Brain gate is an implant system that is developed to assist the people who have limbs loss or lose their bodily functions like patients with spinal cord injury. It is a mind-to-movement system that permits a paralyzed person to regulate a computer using his thoughts [3]. By superlative from both Neuralink is a device that will be surgically implanted in your brain, allowing you to connect with and even control machines. It will also aid in the study of brain electrical impulses and the development of treatments to various medical problems. With neuralink, an 8 mm-diameter chipset called the N1 chipset will be implanted in your skull, with numerous cables containing electrodes and insulation for the wires.

Figure no. 1. Neuralink N1 chip

History Of Neuralink-

Neuralink was founded by Elon Musk and a team of seven scientists and engineers, Neuralink was launched in 2016 and was first publicly reported in March 2017. Jared John Birchall, the wealth manager of Elon Musk was made the President,

CFO and CEO OF Neuralink in 2018. By July 2019, the company had a received a funding of \$158 million, of which \$100 million was from musk himself [2]. As of 2020, the company was located in the Mission District of San Francisco where it shared its headquarters with Open AI, another company co- founded by Elon Musk [4]. in past just similar technology to neuralink called brain gate is facing One of the issues with this technology is that CNPs are implanted directly into the brain tissue. This is a particularly dangerous process since brain tissue is very sensitive. All objects that are inserted into the brain which can damage the parenchyma, the key elements of an organ essential to its functioning. Blood vessels can be damaged and cause micro hemorrhaging during insertion. Neurons can also be ripped and destroyed are the drawbacks of brain gate. Nuralink is general symbiosis between man and a machine or the artificial intelligence. Elon Musk in the launch event of the Neuralink told that the company aims to “understand and treat brainly disorders” along with “preserving and enhancing our brain” and “create a well aligned Figure 2: The Neuralink Logo. Elon Musk in an interview also talked about how the company will try to recreate “the Neural Lace”, a fictional method of transferring brain’s content to a machine and vice-versa [5].

Brain Gate –

Brain gate is an electrode chip that’s implemented in the cortex region of the brain . It is a system developed by cybernetics in 10 years of research, a biotech company in the year 2003 in connection with neuroscience department at Brown University. It helps to exchange the electrical signals between brain and the electrical gadgets. The principle behind this brain implant system is with normal brain functions, brain signals are been generated, but they can’t be sent to arms, hands or legs, these signals are understood and translated to cursor movements, which helps the individual to

regulate the computer by human thoughts. Special software carries all the signaling processes.[6]

Brain gate disadvantages –

- * Costly
- * High risk surgery
- * Not been wireless yet
- * Difficulty in understanding and learning
- * The newest technology is 20bits per minute

Figure no. 3. Brain gate technology

Neuralink –

It is the innovative project involves a multifaceted approach combining neurosurgery, a Brain-chip-interface, and a Brain reading device. Neuralink 's methodology is the thin hair-like structure called 'threads', that connect to the directly in neuron. These wires will be surgically placed inside the brain using a robot, whose wire is thinner than a strand of hair. However, because of its flexibility neuralink's technology is more challenging to implant than the Utah Array. To address this issue, the company has developed "a neurosurgery robot capable of inserting six threads (192 electrodes) every minute," (automatically) It resembles a hybrid between a microscope and a sewing machine in appearance. It also avoids blood

arteries, possibly resulting in a reduced inflammatory response in the brain.

1 Brain machine interface-

Brain Machine Interfaces (BMIs) or Brain Computer Interfaces (BCI) collect, analyse , and interpret brain signals into commands that are communicated to output devices that perform the desired activities . Normal neuromuscular output pathways are not used by Brain Computer Interfaces (BCI). The main goal of BCI is to replace or restore useful function to people disabled by neuromuscular disorders such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis,cerebral palsy, stroke, or spinal cord injury .Brain Machine Interfaces (BMI) or Brain to Machine Interface(B2M) have the potential to assist people with a variety of clinical problems, such as impaired sensory and motor functions as well as connect us to any machine that can read our brain's inputs. For this, we need to have a high bandwidth rate. BMI wasn't initially popular with clinical disorders because of the limited number of channels available for signal transmission, but they now have the potential to aid people with a wide range of clinical problems. Researchers have used no more than 256electrodes to demonstrate human neuro-prosthetic control of computer cursors, robotics limbs, and voice synthesizer Although these successes suggest that high-fidelity Information transfer between brains and machines is possible, development of brain-machine interface has been critically limited by the inability to record from large numbers of neurons.[7]

Figure no 4. A packaged sensor device. (A) Individual neural processing application-specific integrated circuit capable of processing 256 channels of data. This particular packaged device contains 12 of these chips for a total of 3072 channels. (B) Polymer threads on parylene-c substrate. (C) Titanium enclosure (lid removed). (D) Digital USB-C connector for power and data.

2 Structure of neuralink-

2.1 Threads

Threads are the ultra-thin, flexible polymers, which will contain the electrodes and will transfer the signal to the transmitter. Increase production is made possible by wafer-level micro-fabrication which patents the thin film device with 3072 electrodes connected in each wafer. Neuralink contains 48 or 96 threads in each area and each thread contains 32 separate electrodes. Mainly this method is used to stick very integrated chips to the axon part of the neuron which has a higher signal in this area. which is implanted by the surgical robot. Every thread ends with a 16 -50 um square loop to make threading the needle easier. Injecting this type of 1024 electrodes thread into the outside

layer of the brain avoids any veins or arteries. These electrodes communicate with the brain cells which are connected to a Bluetooth link that goes straight outside of the computing device.[8]

2.2 Amplifier-The electrodes are built around the Neuralink custom application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC). Which consists of 256 individually programmable amplifiers on cheap analog to digital converters (ADC) and peripheral control circuitry for serializing the digitized output. These amplifiers play a critical role in accurately capturing and processing brain activity, enabling seamless communication between neurons and the device. By boosting weak electrical signals, the amplifiers ensure reliable data transmission, essential for decoding neural information with precision. Their design focuses on minimizing noise interference and maximizing signal fidelity, crucial for deciphering complex brain patterns. Ultimately, these amplifiers facilitate the seamless exchange of information between the brain and external devices, unlocking the potential for revolutionary advancements in neurotechnology.

Figure no .5. neuralink structure

2.3 How it works

As a result, our brain is made up of neurons that fire all the time in reaction to electrical messages received when we see, hear, move, talk, or think. Every time a neuron fire in response to these electrical signals, a little electromagnetic field is created. Neuralink will essentially tap into the brain's small electric field generated by sinus junctions. To detect these action potential tiny threads with electrodes that are about one-tenth the cross section of a human hair or roughly the size of a neuron are developed and injected into the brain. Each thread will be inserted by a r robot to avoid bursting blood vessels or causing stress. The insertion needle is 24 microns in diameter, which is significantly smaller than the current state-of-the-art in deep brain stimulation The processor for making all of this work is called the n1 chip. The n1 chip amplifies, digitizes, analyses, and transfers analogue brain signals captured by the threads to a pod device behind the ear. The pod device is the only thing that will be upgraded, and the implants will remain in place until the pod is removed and everything goes down. The n1 chip is a low-power 4 by 5millimetre chip with built-in technology for processing brain data. It can read 20,000 brain samples per second, indicating that these are true raw signals from a neuralink attached to a brain.

Because the neural link comprises thousands of electrodes, it produces a cleaner, more dependable signal for more complicated application. The neural link's first application will be to tap into the primary motor cortex, which is the part of the brain that sends signals down to the spinal cord and onto the muscles to drive movement. It will start with simple things like a mouse and keyboard, but it could also be used to read signals from all movement, including speech, and finally it could be used to restore movement in someone's own body The materials or qualities that would cause the brain to not only accept but also believe that the neuralink is a part of it [9].

2.4 Robot -

The "Robot" is designed with a sole purpose of inserting the threads in least invasive manner. The Robot consists of seven parts-

- a) Loaded needle pincher cartridge.
- b) Low-force contact brain position sensor.
- c) Light modules with multiple independent wavelengths.
- d) Needle motor.
- e) One of four cameras focused on the needle during insertion.
- f) Camera with wide angle view of surgical field.
- g) Stereoscopic3cameras.

Figure no. 6. The robotic electrode inserter; enlarged view of the inserter-head shown in the inset. (A) Loaded needle pincher cartridge. (B) Low-force contact brain position sensor. (C) Light modules with multiple independent wavelengths. (D) Needle motor. (E) One of four cameras

focused on the needle during insertion. (F) Camera with wide angle view of the surgical field. (G) Stereoscopic cameras Neuralink has developed a robotic insertion approach for inserting flexible probes (or threads), allowing fast and reliable insertion of large numbers of threads targeted to

avoid vasculature and record from dispersed brain regions. [1] For the insertion, the Robot has a “needle pincher” assembly which inserts the thread, stitches it and releases it rapidly. To guide

the needle, the Robot has four camera which are focused on the needle, the field of insertion, and stereoscopy.

Figure 7. Insertion process into an agarose brain proxy. (1) The inserter approaches the brain proxy with a thread. (i) needle and cannula. (ii) Previously inserted thread. (2) Inserter touches down on the brain proxy surface. (3) Needle penetrates tissue proxy, advancing the thread to the desired depth. (iii) Inserting thread. (4) Inserter pulls away, leaving the thread behind in the tissue proxy. (iv) Inserted thread.

2.5 DISCUSSION

The robot’s insertion head is mounted on a globally accurate, $400 \times 400 \times 150$ mm travel, $10 \mu\text{m}$ three-axis stage and holds a small, quick-swappable “needle-pincher” assembly. The needle is milled from $40 \mu\text{m}$ diameter tungsten-rhenium

wire-stock electrochemically etched to $24 \mu\text{m}$ diameter along the inserted length the tip of the needle is designed both to hook onto insertion loops-for transporting and inserting individual threads-and to penetrate the meninges and brain tissue. The needle is driven by a linear motor, allowing variable insertion speeds and rapid retraction acceleration (up to $30,000 \text{ mm/s}^2$) to encourage separation of the probe from the needle. The pincher is a $50 \mu\text{m}$ tungsten wire bent at the tip and driven both axially and rotationally. It serves as a support for probes during transport and as a guide to ensure that threads are inserted along the needle path.

Figure no. 8 . how neuralink works

Neuralink Clinical Trials On Living Animals-

1. Animal Tests -

Since 2017, Neuralink has been testing the N1 chip by planting it in the brains of monkeys, pigs and other animals. From 2017 to 2020, Neuralink

carried out these experiments in partnership with University of California, Davis (commonly known as UC DAVIS). Twenty-three monkeys were experimented on, out of which seven were transferred by the university to Neuralink at the

end of their partnership. The initial success of these experiments was publicly confirmed in April 2021 when Elon Musk posted a video of a nine-year-old macaque monkey named Pager playing the video game Pong with its mind, with the help of the brain implant. They made this progress by compensating Pager with a banana smoothie at whatever point it finished a progression of undertakings in the game [10]. Then, at that point, the joysticks were detached, however Pager's psyche actually continued to convey similar messages to accept its prize i.e., the smoothie. These signs sent by the cerebrum permitted Pager to play the game through the mind chip, with next to no joysticks. In July 2023, Musk affirmed that these monkeys are currently fit for playing more perplexing computer games like Minecraft through their psyches. Experimentation has also been done on pigs. Electrodes were implanted in a pig's spinal cord which allowed the engineers to control the movement of the pig's limbs showing that the chip can be used to cure full body paralysis. Criticism and the Ethical Issues of these tests

Neuralink's experiments have been criticized by many animal rights and safety organizations including the People for the Ethical Treatment of Animals which is more commonly referred to as PETA [11]. In 2022, the Physicians Committee for Responsible Medicine (PCRM) claimed that Neuralink and UC Davis had mistreated a number of monkeys, putting them through mental anguish, excruciating pain, and chronic infections as a result of surgery. PCRM believes that the fifteen monkeys which were not transferred to Neuralink were killed during the experimentation. In December 2022, Neuralink was reportedly the subject of a Agriculture (USDA) on possible breaches of Animal Welfare.[12] A report also states that the employees were rushed due to Elon Musk's demands of fast reports which caused a lot of unnecessary harm and pain to these animals. Neuralink denied all these claims by stating that all the monkeys that passed away died after the experimentation was over, and not during the experimentation.

Figure no. 9: pager playing with pong with its mind

2 Human Trials

Initially, in 2022, the application for clinical human trials of the chip was rejected by The United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) due to its incomplete information on the implant effect on the human body. However, in June 2023, The FDA approved clinical human trials. "The FDA acknowledges and understands that Neuralink has announced that its investigational device exemption for its

implant/R1 robot was approved by the FDA and that it may now begin conducting human clinical trials for its device," said an agency spokesperson.[13] On January 29, 2024, it was announced by Elon Musk that the implantation of neuralink into the human brain as a brain-computer interface will play a vital role in the advancement of neuroscience and neurobiology. Musk said on space that the person on whom this first trial was made is reluctantly in a full recovery

zone with no ill effects and is also able to move a mouse around the screen by just thinking. While the human implantation was done and recruitment was going on for a large sample clinical trial, the scientists discovered that this device has potential in the treatment of Parkinson disease.[14]

How Neuralink Symbiosis In Disease Curing-

Neuralink can play a crucial role in treating neurodegenerative disorder by the advanced mechanism of neuralink. it treats Parkinson's, epilepsy, Alzheimer's like diseases. Specifically, multielectrode neuro interfaces may become the basis for new communication systems and advanced assistive technologies for paralyzed people as well as control external devices and interact with the entire environment. eg- by integrating into new fast developed technologies, such as Smart Home and Internet of Things. Moreover, the brain-computer interface applications are very promising for detecting hidden information in the user's brain, which cannot be revealed by conventional communication channels. Currently, the use of noninvasive brain-computer interfaces in these fields is limited by a low number of commands that can be recognized. This limitation arises from a relatively small number of commands that can be recognized. This limitation arises from a relatively small number of features, which can be extracted from the scalp-level electroencephalography or functional near-infrared spectroscopy recordings. The invasive brain-computer interfaces (or brain-machine interfaces) demonstrate much better performance than noninvasive brain-computer interfaces; however, they require a larger number of channels to obtain more detailed information about the individual spiking activity of the neurons across distributed cortical regions. The device reported in the paper of Elon Musk and Neuralink approaches the solution to this problem.

1 Epilepsy-

Epilepsy is neuronal disorder in which the brain is the center that controls and regulates all voluntary and involuntary responses in the body. It consists of nerve cells that normally communicate with each other through electrical activity. A seizure occurs when part(s) of the brain receives a burst of abnormal electrical signals that temporarily interrupts normal electrical brain function.

to predict epileptic seizures, the neuronal activity must be recorded from predefined focal areas of the brain, where an earlier manifestation of this pathological activity is mostly pronounced and can be promptly detected in real time. Recently, an efficient method for epilepsy prediction based on electrical brain activity was proposed. The method allows forecasting a focal seizure up to 5 seconds before it occurs. This time is sufficient for a brain-machine interface to generate a proper signal, which suppresses the forthcoming seizure. For drug-resistant patients, the complete abolishment of epileptic seizures might be achieved by a brain-machine interface/brain-computer interface that predicts a seizure onset, combined with a system that interferes with the process that causes the seizure. Thus, seizure prediction remains an unresolved problem due to insufficient information about neural processes in the onset brain area. Therefore, one possible and very important clinical application of the Neuralink technology is a brain-machine interface for patients with drug-resistant epilepsy. These brain-machine interfaces should imply the brain stimulation (electrical, magnetic, optogenetics, etc.) to interrupt or even prevent epileptic seizures. The stimulation can be delivered to the brain in either an open-loop or a closed-loop fashion. In the former case, there is no need to monitor the current brain activity, since the stimulation is activated manually or in accordance with a predefined stimulation protocol.

Figure 10. The schematic illustration of brain-machine interface prototypes to suppress epileptic seizures using electrical stimulation. (a) Vagus nerve stimulator containing (1) an implantable pulse generator and (2) a stimulation lead. (b) Stimulator of the anterior nucleus of the thalamus in epilepsy containing (1) an implantable pulse generator and (2) intracranial electrodes placed in the anterior thalamic nuclei bilaterally. (c) Responsive neurostimulator containing (1) implanted deep electrodes for recording electroencephalography signals, (2) an implantable device for processing electroencephalography signals from electrodes, and (3) strip electrodes receiving an electrical stimulation signal generated by the device to stop seizures. As an example of the open-loop system, in Figure 10a, we present the vagus nerve stimulator manufactured by Cyberonics, Inc (Texas, United States) in 1977. The stimulator contains an implantable pulse generator and an electrode to stimulate the left vagus nerve in a repetitive “duty cycle” (“on” for 30 seconds and then “off” for 5 minutes), which allows reducing the number of seizures by an average of 30%–40%. Along with the vagus nerve stimulator, other open-loop antiepileptic devices are also used for deep brain stimulation. One of the first open-loop deep brain stimulators was the stimulator of the anterior nucleus of the thalamus in epilepsy proposed by Medtronic, Inc (United States) for patients with partial-onset epilepsy [15] (Figure 10b).

Although the open-loop systems enable a significant reduction in the number of epileptic seizures, it is obvious that a more efficient control of epileptic activity requires continuous monitoring of the current brain activity, which can be achieved by using closed-loop brain-machine interfaces. One of the first closed-loop brain-machine interfaces was the responsive neurostimulator designed by Neuropace Inc. (California, United States; Figure 10c). It contains implanted electrodes for recording the intracranial electroencephalography used by the algorithm, which determines the moment of time when a seizure starts. To interrupt the seizure, the triggered focal electrical stimulation is sent to a specific brain area.[16] It is important to point out that epileptic seizures are well detected using electrocorticography or intracranial electroencephalography, which display a pronounced marker of the high-amplitude rhythmic activity. Recent studies reported a 100% accuracy of this technique in detecting epileptic seizures in rats. Since the pre-ictal activity may not differ from a normal behavior, the prediction of seizures is a very challenging task. Although existing algorithms allow seizure predictions with high sensitivity, they are too complicated and too specific to be used in clinics. One of the closed-loop systems for the seizure prediction and prevention was recently tested in vivo in rats (Figure 11). The seizure prediction algorithm was based on the electrocorticography signals recorded by three electrodes in the cortex and the thalamus, as shown in Figure 11a. The brain-machine

interface was able to correctly predict 45% seizures, but the number of false predictions varied from 20 to 100 per hour among animals. In this regard, one can expect that the technique developed by Elon Musk and Neuralink with thousands of channels will significantly improve seizure prediction. The large number of registered channels will increase classification accuracy in pre-epileptic state recognition and decrease the number of false positives during light slow wave sleep. This is indeed a step toward the next

generation of brain-machine interfaces for drug-resistant epilepsy. The accurate seizure prediction algorithm based on the multichannel Neuralink technology enables the prevention of ongoing seizures and protects the patient against unnecessary stimulations caused by false alarms. Thanks to the developed brain-machine interface platform with thousands of channels, significant progress is expected in solving this important problem, enabling new clinical trials for patients resistant to drug therapy.[17]

Figure 11. (a) Schematic representation of the experiments with a rat. (b) The set of electrocorticography recordings taken from sub granular layers 4 (Ctx4) and 5 (Ctx5) of the somatosensory cortex and postero/lateral thalamus before and during onset of the epileptic spike-wave discharge. (c) Histological verification of the electrode location in the somatosensory cortex (S1) and postero/lateral thalamus.

2. Tinnitus -

Tinnitus is a neurological disorder where ringing or buzzing in the ears in the absence of an external source is seen. It happens when the nerve that connects the inner ear with the brain, known as the vestibulocochlear nerve, is damaged due to extended loud noise, injury or deficiencies in blood supply. Elon Musk has claimed the Neuralink device could cure tinnitus by 2027. He states on X "Definitely. Might be less than 5 years away, as the current version Neuralinks are semi-

generalized neural read/write devices with ~1000 electrodes and tinnitus probably need <<1000.

Future gen Neuralinks will increase electrode count by many orders of magnitude." These claims might appear impressive. Yet the underlying science is not feisty. In summary, the novel neurointerface by Elon Musk and NeuroLink has all chances to become a real step forward to the next generation of brain-machine interfaces for both research and clinical applications. Invasive interfaces can help disabled people control external devices and communicate with other people. We believe that future communication technologies will be based on brain-computer interfaces that will read brain signals and translate them to messages, which then will be sent to mobile or other devices. Furthermore, invasive brain-machine interfaces will allow a direct communication between people by their thoughts.

Application Of Neuralink-

In the process of developing neuralink N1, a handful of team members of this project took internet as their flat form to explain the process and applications of this brain machine interface and neuralink. The applications mainly consist of following

1. For Visual Orthotic

As per report of neuralink team stated that this project has that ability to provide a visual

prosthesis for people who have retinal injury or myopia through eye injury. This idea is to eventually seal a cornea directly into the visual cortex and stimulating the signals to recognize the objects. Practically this happens by adjusting the frequency and wavelength firmly to the sensor to have a artificial eyesight.

Figure no12. application of neuralink with actual cortical part involve

2. Telepathy

From the view of one of the main chip designers at neuralink telepathy can be the next frontier for neuralink. Musk stated to put this technology of words into efforts it needs lot of efforts and ideas. This plan basically depends on sending one’s true thoughts and communicating with each other’s brains. Telepathy is commonly known as nonlinguistic communication or nonverbal sharing of thought with one another.

3. Oscilloscope for Brain Interface

Oscilloscopes allow visual information of printed circuit boards (pcds). Similarly, the neuralink device can process many functions of the brain. “The side effect of the device is you will end up learning a lot about how the brain actually works” stated one of the term members of neuralink project.

4. Unlocking Hidden Creativity

As debated in case of telepathy our communication system is not efficient as expected when it comes to translating. As one of the

forefront research projects said that there is a lot of untapped creativity is present in each one of us. As for the instance when a person has some plan for some project that you had it in your mind which is non explainable but when you close your eyes it is easy for you to imagine the exact output, you’re expecting from the project in such cases neuralink helps to decode your thoughts and helps you to present it out. This all can be done with the help of artificial intelligence.

5. Abolishing Pain

One of the neurosurgeons who were there at the moment the neuralink event stated about the pain which leading many to suffer and causing many mental health problems like depression etc. In today’s world mental illness is the most common disease most in teens. Even the treatment given to cure this pain is also painfull to endure. But this can be easily cured by letting one to forget the things which are causing pain, depression and other mental issues through neuralink device.[20]

Future Of Neuralink-

Receiving and transcribing the information from over 3,000 electrodes proves another daunting task. The Neuralink device must be capable of recording, digitizing, and amplifying small neural signals ($<10 \mu\text{VRMS}$) while filtering out-of-band noise and streaming these signals out for real-time processing while still being compact and low power. The Neuralink device consists of 256 individually programmable amplifiers, on-chip-to-digital converters, and peripheral control circuitry for serializing the digitized outputs. Neuralink uses a custom online spike-detection software to decode and display the signals. The signals are displayed on a graph with each row corresponding to an electrode site on the thread. The future of the Neuralink brain chip holds the potential to revolutionize the way we interact with technology and understand the brain. When we wrote this in August 2024, Neuralink was still emerging and being tested in humans, so our response will be based on the potential future impacts/applications as what we knew at that time. Possible applications of the Neuralink N1 chip in pharmaceutical science and research were as following.

1. Drug development and testing:

For instance, the chip might offer information on how a drug influences neural activity that would otherwise take days to manifest during the slow trial-and-error of drug development. It could also enable a more accurate tracking of the effects that drugs have on different brain areas or neural routes.

.2. Personalized medicine:

With the N1 chip, it will be possible to customize the drug treatments according to personal brain activity patterns. It can help identify who needs the intervention most. [18]

Elon Musk has expressed optimism about the future of Neuralink, his brain-computer interface company, predicting widespread adoption of its brain chip within the next decade. This follows encouraging progress with the second recipient of

the implant, who is reportedly experiencing significant improvements in his ability to interact with digital devices. "If all goes well, there will be hundreds of people with Neuralinks within a few years, maybe tens of thousands within 5 years, millions within 10 years," Musk stated on X (formerly Twitter). Looking ahead, Neuralink plans to expand the chip's capabilities to interact with the physical world, allowing users to control robotic arms or wheelchairs, enhancing their independence. "Additionally, we plan to enable the Link to interact with the physical world, allowing users to feed themselves and move more independently by controlling a robotic arm or their wheelchair," the company shared.

Downside -

While the implant has many positive attributes, Last, but not the least, are the unpleasant consequences of this work that we should pay attention to, since every achievement of humanity has two sides. On one hand, it intends to improve the quality of life, but on the other hand, it can be used by unscrupulous people for their selfish goals. Therefore, every scientist should think not only about a positive impact of his/her research, but also about its possible negative effects. Among the undesired effects of brain-machine interfaces with electrodes implanted into the human brain is the possibility that a government or a nongovernmental organization will control and manipulate the person's behavior not only through mass media, but also by directly sending commands to the brain. In this regard, numerous debates about ethics of using brain-machine interfaces are currently underway in the media.

1. Killing of animals

One of the main downsides of the implant is the killing of animals during testing. Leaked documents showed that nearly 1,500 animals were killed during the testing of the implant.

2. Loss of humanity

If these chips do become as advanced as Elon Musk claims, our reliability on the machines will keep on increasing. The more reliable on the chip we become, the less human are.

3. Viruses and bugs

There is a chance of the implant getting a virus or a bug which could lead to slowing down of processing of brain and body functions. How will these viruses or bugs be removed without harming the brain?

4. Feeling of Inferiority

What if someone does not want an implant? If the implant does turn out to be successful, the people with the implant will have more physical and mental abilities. This will create a feeling of inferiority among the people without implants. There will also be a bias against these people.

5. Hacking

The most prominent and dangerous threat of the brain chips is hacking. Any smart gadget can be hacked by people with the ability to do so. But, the hacking of the brain chip will be nothing like the hacking of a smart gadget like a laptop or a phone. If a normal smart gadget is hacked, the hacker only gets access to the information and files present in that particular device. However, if a brain chip does get hacked, the hacker would have access to your brain which in turn gives access to the entire body. The hacker would be able to control the entire body functioning, allowing the hacker to make functions of the organs faster, slow them down or even stop them entirely. Along with this, the hacker would have access to and could alter or delete any thoughts, emotions, memories. This can allow the hacker to control the actions of the person including what the person sees, hears, smells, thinks, feels.

CONCLUSION-

Neuralink may be the bridge that connects medical field to the next level of Artificial Intelligence, now we can neuralink chip practically study the electrical signals in brains and arrive at solution

that can help to to cure so many lives suffering from neural disabilities or various medical problems. It used brain signal to communicate with outside the world. On January 29, 2024 chip was successfully implanted in person on whom this 1st trial was made is reluctantly in a full recovery zone with no ill and also able to move a mouse around the screen by just thinking.

In our present society, if we truly concern about someone's liberty, individual space and privacy we need to give a high standard throughout brain machine interfaces. The words 'threat' and 'responsibility' are very much critical while dealing with this technology. As there are many advantages over this technology there are disadvantages too. Ultimately, the future of the neuralink brain chip not only on technological advancements but ethical, legal and social implementation. Thoughtfully responsible. If managed effectively the Neuralink brain chip could pave the way for unprecedented advancements in our understanding of the brain and the enhancement of human capabilities.

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